

FIELD TESTING OF PILES FOR HORIZONTAL LOAD, TAKING INTO ACCOUNT THE SOAKING OF THE SOIL**S. Nyamdorj,
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11000. Ulaanbaatar. Building-T. MSUST.**Abstract**

In recent years, the Orkhon-Selengsky region, especially the city of Darkhan, in whose territories loess-like subsiding soils are widespread, are actively being built and it is planned to build an ASG and imperial structures to regulate the problems of overpopulation and smoke in the city of Ulaanbaatar, the capital of Mongolia. In connection with these, the tasks of an experimental-theoretical study of the work of piles for various combinations of loads, taking into account the soaking of subsiding foundation soils, are acutely posed. This report discusses the results of field tests and numerical solutions of 2 bored piles with a length of 8.0 m and a diameter of 0.6 m for a horizontal load under conditions of preliminary soaking of subsiding soil in order to determine the values of the ultimate load and the magnitude of the horizontal displacement.

Keywords: silty sandy loam soil, horizontal movement, preliminary soil soaking, elastic deformation

Introduction

The main regional feature of loess-like subsiding soils in the territory of Mongolia is that in their natural state they have a kyrogenic sublimation origin, low humidity and high fragmentation (Dashzhamts [1]; Nyamdorzh [2; 3]), which, under the conditions of inevitable technogenic soaking and by subsidence (Bagdasarov and Nyamdorzh [4]), and soaked loess clayey soils during seasonal deep freezing give heaving in different degrees and during thawing, intermeasured precipitation is formed (Tsytoovich et al. [5]; Bagdasarov [6]). As a result of these negative factors, many houses are overwhelmed, as a rule, by uneven, unacceptable precipitation and deformation, significant funds and time are spent to eliminate the latter. Unfortunately, as a result of reinforcement and repair work, buildings are sometimes not fully restored as required in regulatory documents (Znamensky [7]; Gotman [8]; Polyankin [9]), especially in relation to SNIIP for the design of buildings and structures in seismically active areas, according to since the territory of Mongolia has a high seismic activity.

Therefore, of considerable scientific and practical interest are studies of the engineering-geological and construction properties of loess-like subsiding soils in Mongolia, models and methods for calculating design, methods for experimental determination of the bearing capacity and settlement of experimental pile and other types of foundations under different modes of loading and soaking of the foundation soil (Grigoryan [10]; Bagdasarov & Nyamdorj [11]; Mangushev et al. [12]; Basu and Salgado [13]).

Engineering and geological conditions

Engineering and geological conditions of the experimental site of bored piles for a horizontal load. In August and September 2020, we conducted field tests of 2 bored piles for a horizontal load, the experimental site is located next to the building of the Darkhan branch of MSUNT, where loess-like subsidence silty sandy loam is common. Physical and mechanical characteristics of the soils of the experimental site are given in Table 1.

Table of physical and mechanical indicators of soils

№	Indicators	Index	Unit of measure.	Silty sandy loam	Gravelly loam
1	Natural humidity	W	fract. units.	0,051	0,070
2	Porosity coefficient	e	fract. units.	0,59	0,42
3	Degree of humidity	S_r	fract. units.	0,41	0,48
4	Average humidity after soaking	W_{sat}	fract. units.	0,16	0,082
5	Average degree of humidity after soaking	S_r''	fract. units.	0,87	0,56
6	Adhesive force	C'	kPa	20,8	22,4
		C''	kPa	6,8	
7	Angle of internal friction	φ'	degree	23	2,7
		φ''	degree	17	
8	Deformation modulus	E	mPa	11	23
		E_{sat}	mPa	4,2	
9	Design resistance	R_o	kPa	200	350

Methods and materials

For testing, 2 bored piles with a diameter of 0.6 m and a length of 8.0 m were concreted using a casing pipe with a diameter of 0.62 m. The casing pipe was removed after concreting. Concrete class B20 without additive, class of working reinforcement A450, transverse reinforcement A240. After a 3-day curing of concrete, dimples with a size of 1.5x1.5x0.3 (h) were dug around each pile, after which, for 34 days, about 10 m³ of water was continuously poured into the city pipeline to soak the soil.

Before the start of the test, a well was drilled for sampling and the moisture content near the pile soil was determined. According to the results of moisture determination, the soils were moistened to the value of the water-saturated state (Table 1). The pile was loaded with a horizontal load using a D-100 hydraulic jack, in 6 steps from 2.5 tons to 15.0 tons. The tests were continued up to 40 mm horizontal displacement ($U_u=40$ mm) according to the standard procedure "BNbD 50.01-16; MNS 3388-1982; SP 24.13330.2011".

Fig1. Testing a pile for a horizontal load from soaking the base soil.

Results of field tests

Horizontal displacements were measured at the initial moment ($t=0$) and further at each time interval under loadings $Q=2.5 \div 15.0$ tons in steps of 2.5 t. After the

end of the tests, after 3 hours, a 15.0 tons load was unloaded in steps of 5.0 tons and the elastic displacement was measured (Fig. 2; 3). The results of tests of bored piles for horizontal load are shown in Figure 2÷4

Fig 2. Graph of dependence $U=f(Q)$ piles I and II

Fig 3. Average dependence graph $U=f(Q)$ piles I and II

Fig 4. Averaged dependence curves $U=f(t)$ of piles I and II under the action loads $Q= 2.5\div 15.0$ тн.

For comparison with the results of full-scale tests of bored piles for a horizontal load in pre-soaked subsiding silty sandy loamy soils, numerical experiments were carried out using the PLAXIS 2D calculation software package (PLAXIS official website [14]) and the

work of the foundation soils and piles was modeled by the finite element method (Fadeev A. B. [15]). Soil conditions are shown in Table 1. Numerical test results are shown in Figure 5-8.

Fig 5. Horizontal movement of soil under the action of $Q_6 = 150$ Kn

Fig 6. Graphics of horizontal movements of piles. $U_x=38.49\text{mm}$

Fig 7. Graphics of transverse forces in piles. $Q_x=79.58\text{KN}$

Fig 8. Graphics of bending moments in piles. $M_x=262.9\text{KNm}$

Conclusions from the results

1. Based on the test results, it was established that the maximum horizontal load of a bored pile-I and pile-II with a length of 8.0 m and a diameter of 0.6 m in previously soaked loess-like silty sandy loamy soils is 15.0 tons. According to the conditions of permissible horizontal displacements of the I pile $U_u=40\text{mm} > U_t^{p.I}=38.723\text{mm}$, for the II piles $U_u=40\text{mm} > U_t^{p.II}=36.605\text{mm}$. The average value of the horizontal displacement of piles I and II at loads of 15.0 tons $U_t^{AV} = 38,164\text{mm}$.

2. Immediately after loading at $t=0$, horizontal displacements proceed intensively, moderately during the first 2 hours, later, under loads of 10.0 ÷ 15.0 tons, after 2 hours of loading, horizontal displacements increase. The increase in horizontal displacements to certain values is due to the activation of pore water squeezing by

primary filtration consolidation, which arises from pressure due to specified loads in stages from 2.5 tons to 15.0 tons.

3. The magnitude of elastic displacements during unloading from 15.0 tons to 0.0 tons for pile I is 9.658 mm, for pile II it is 9.087 mm, the average value is 9.523 mm. The magnitude of elastic displacements is about 25% of the magnitude of the horizontal displacement. From this we can conclude that elastic deformation occurs due to elastic work, the remaining pore water after incomplete primary filtration consolidation in the horizontal direction.

4. According to the results of numerical solutions under the action of the ultimate horizontal load, the displacement $U_x=38.49\text{mm}$, the horizontal force $Q_x=79.58\text{KN}$, the bending moment $M_x=262.9\text{KNm}$. The value of the discrepancy between the horizontal displacements of numerical solutions compared with the results of full-scale field tests is less than 5.0%, which corresponds to the allowable limit.

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